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STATISTICAL OVERVIEW OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION SECTOR ADVANCEMENTS IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN REGION (2008-2018)

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Abstract:

This scientific article presents a comprehensive statistical analysis of the Information and Communication Sector in the Romanian Mountain Region over the ten-year period from 2008 to 2018. The study aims to provide insights into the advancements, trends, and key developments within this sector, shedding light on the region's technological and communicative landscape.

1. Introduction:

The Information and Communication Sector play a pivotal role in shaping regional development, fostering innovation, and enhancing connectivity. This article focuses on the Romanian Mountain Region, examining statistical data spanning from 2008 to 2018 to discern patterns and changes within the sector.

2. Methodology:

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The research employs a quantitative approach, utilizing a range of statistical tools and metrics to analyze data collected from governmental reports, industry publications, and relevant databases. Key indicators such as infrastructure growth, technological adoption rates, and economic contributions are examined to provide a nuanced understanding of the sector's evolution.

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3. Infrastructure Development:

This section delves into the expansion of information and communication infrastructure within the Romanian Mountain Region. The analysis encompasses the growth of broadband networks, the proliferation of mobile technology, and the establishment of data centers, offering a comprehensive perspective on the region's connectivity.

4. Technological Adoption Rates:

Examining the adoption rates of emerging technologies within the Information and Communication Sector, this section explores the integration of innovations such as cloud computing, artificial intelligence, and the Internet of Things. Insights into the impact of these technologies on regional development and economic growth are discussed.

5. Economic Contributions:

The economic significance of the Information and Communication Sector in the Romanian Mountain Region is assessed through the examination of its contributions to GDP, employment rates, and entrepreneurial activities. This section highlights the sector's role as a driver of economic development and its influence on job creation.

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6. Trends and Challenges:

Identifying notable trends and challenges encountered by the Information and Communication Sector during the specified period, this section provides a forward-looking perspective on potential future developments. Factors influencing the sector, such as regulatory changes and global technological shifts, are explored.

7. Results:

The statistics for the Information and communication sectors (figures) present for each sector separately ascending values for the mean and median, the other statistical indicators having sometimes antagonistic fluctuations (statistical values for Average, Std Error. to mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Skewness, Kurtosis, Variance, Minimum, Maximum, Percentile 50 Value; they are repeated for each indicator separately), as follows: mean of 34730.56, standard error of the mean 1561.672, median 35215.00, standard deviation 4685.017, variance 21949387.028, Skewness -.403, standard error of Skewness .717, Kurtosis -.001, standard error of Kurtosis

1.400, distance 15063, minimum 26482, maximum 41545, percentile 25 - 31573.00, 50 - 35215 -30.05, 45.605

The presented values demonstrate that the Information and communication sectors in the mountain area have a good development in Romania for the population of active enterprises. Some sectors also show negative values, the overall picture showing a good overall mountain business situation for the industry.

The central tendency of the Information and communication sectors of the economy during the analyzed period shows that the population of active enterprises in mountainous Romania has grown considerably from 2008 to 2019. The statistics related to this indicator show a high degree of non-variability, which means that the results do not show a large deviation and are positive. The corresponding symmetrical distributions lead to the idea that the business environment begins to stabilize considerably during the analyzed period. Kurtosis with a low standard error represents crowding in some industries.

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Figure 2.7.1. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Romania for S7 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.7.2. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Macroregion one of Romania for S7 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.7.3. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Macroregion two of Romania for S7 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.7.4. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in the third Macroregion of Romania for S7 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.7.5. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in the fourth Macroregion of Romania for S7 in the period 2008-2019

The forecast analysis for the secondary, tertiary and quaternary sectors in the mountainous area of Romania indicates that they will have a continuous growth until 2030. Both at the national, macro-regional, regional and county level, the models resulting from the statistical modeling show certain areas montana are more sustainable than others. The fit statistic shows relevant values for mean, standard error, minimum, maximum, and 5/10 percentiles (presented in that order below), as follows: Stationary R-squared .167 .312, -.109, .811, -.014, -2.220E-16; R-square .813, .090, .572, 1.000, .627, .668; RMSE 167,519, 278,286, .000, 1597,919, 15,041, 16,432; MAPS 8,732, 3,329, .000, 15,416, 3,095, 3,660; MaxAPE 28,769, 11,531, .000, 50,019, 8,572, 11,430; MAE 114,541, 186,949, .000, 1043,125, 10,946, 11,153;

MaxAE 354,439, 570,884, .000, 3172,875, 25,469, 34,754; Normalized BIC 8.844, 2.457, 5.782, 15.013, 5.818, 5.916.

Table. Forecast analysis of mountain entrepreneurship in the mountain area of Romania for S7

Model		Forecast										
		2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030
Romania-Model_1	Forecast	43428	45311	47194	49077	50959	52842	54725	56608	58491	60374	62257
	UCL	47206	50654	53738	56633	59408	62098	64722	67295	69826	72322	74788
	LCL	39649	39967	40649	41520	42510	43587	44728	45921	47155	48425	49725
Macroregiunea unu-Model_2	Forecast	12455	13025	13595	14166	14736	15306	15876	16446	17016	17586	18156
	UCL	13604	14650	15586	16464	17305	18121	18916	19696	20464	21220	21968
	LCL	11306	11400	11605	11867	12166	12491	12835	13196	13569	13952	14345
Nord-Vest-Model_3	Forecast	7631	8063	8494	8926	9358	9790	10222	10654	11085	11517	11949
	UCL	9116	10163	11066	11896	12678	13427	14150	14854	15540	16213	16874
	LCL	6146	5963	5922	5956	6038	6153	6293	6454	6631	6821	7024
Bihor-Model_4	Forecast	1122	1178	1234	1290	1346	1402	1459	1515	1571	1627	1683
	UCL	1268	1325	1382	1439	1496	1552	1609	1666	1723	1780	1837
	LCL	975	1031	1086	1141	1197	1252	1308	1363	1419	1474	1530
Bistrita-Nasaud-Model_5	Forecast	388	411	433	456	478	501	523	546	568	591	613
	UCL	490	555	610	660	706	750	793	834	874	913	951
	LCL	287	267	257	252	251	251	254	258	263	268	275
Cluj-Model_6	Forecast	4627	4903	5178	5454	5730	6006	6282	6558	6833	7109	7385
	UCL	5477	6105	6651	7155	7632	8089	8532	8963	9384	9798	10205
	LCL	3776	3700	3706	3754	3829	3923	4032	4152	4282	4420	4565
Maramures-Model_7	Forecast	731	768	806	843	881	918	956	993	1031	1068	1106

	UCL	943	1069	1174	1269	1357	1440	1519	1596	1670	1742	1812
	LCL	518	467	437	417	405	397	393	391	392	395	400
Satu Mare-Model_8	Forecast	399	419	440	460	481	501	522	542	563	583	604
	UCL	497	558	610	657	700	742	782	820	857	894	930
	LCL	300	280	270	264	261	261	262	265	268	273	278
Salaj-Model_9	Forecast	369	391	412	434	456	478	500	522	543	565	587
	UCL	439	490	535	575	614	651	686	721	755	788	821
	LCL	298	291	290	293	298	305	313	322	332	342	353
Centru-Model_10	Forecast	4917	5148	5379	5610	5841	6072	6303	6534	6765	6996	7227
	UCL	5816	6419	6936	7408	7851	8274	8682	9077	9462	9839	10209
	LCL	4018	3877	3822	3812	3831	3870	3924	3991	4068	4153	4245
Alba-Model_11	Forecast	539	566	592	619	646	673	700	727	753	780	807
	UCL	705	801	880	952	1018	1080	1140	1197	1252	1306	1358
	LCL	373	331	305	287	274	266	260	256	255	254	256
Brasov-Model_12	Forecast	1453	1519	1584	1650	1715	1781	1846	1911	1977	2042	2108
	UCL	1611	1677	1742	1808	1873	1939	2004	2069	2135	2200	2266
	LCL	1295	1361	1426	1492	1557	1623	1688	1753	1819	1884	1950
Covasna-Model_13	Forecast	333	348	364	379	395	410	426	441	457	472	488
	UCL	387	425	457	488	516	543	569	595	619	644	668
	LCL	278	271	270	271	274	278	282	288	294	301	308
Harghita-Model_14	Forecast	543	569	595	621	646	672	698	724	749	775	801
	UCL	629	655	681	707	734	760	786	812	838	864	891
	LCL	458	483	509	534	559	585	610	635	661	686	711
Mures-Model_15	Forecast	1023	1078	1134	1190	1245	1301	1356	1412	1468	1523	1579
	UCL	1216	1352	1469	1577	1678	1775	1868	1959	2048	2135	2221
	LCL	829	805	799	803	813	827	845	865	887	911	937

Sibiu-Model_16	Forecast	977	1026	1075	1124	1172	1221	1270	1319	1367	1416	1465
	UCL	1183	1233	1283	1332	1382	1432	1482	1531	1581	1631	1680
	LCL	772	820	867	915	963	1010	1058	1106	1154	1201	1249
Macroregiunea doi-Model_17	Forecast	6854	7131	7407	7684	7961	8238	8514	8791	9068	9345	9621
	UCL	7582	8160	8668	9140	9588	10020	10440	10850	11251	11646	12035
	LCL	6126	6101	6147	6228	6333	6455	6588	6732	6884	7043	7207
Nord-Est-Model_18	Forecast	4350	4577	4803	5030	5256	5483	5709	5936	6162	6389	6615
	UCL	5253	5854	6367	6835	7275	7694	8098	8489	8870	9243	9609
	LCL	3448	3300	3240	3224	3238	3271	3321	3382	3454	3534	3621
Bacau-Model_19	Forecast	604	629	655	680	706	731	757	782	808	833	859
	UCL	731	809	875	935	991	1044	1094	1143	1190	1237	1282
	LCL	476	449	434	425	421	419	420	422	425	430	436
Botosani-Model_20	Forecast	301	317	333	349	365	381	397	413	429	445	461
	UCL	351	368	385	402	418	435	452	469	486	503	520
	LCL	251	266	281	296	311	326	341	357	372	387	402
Iasi-Model_21	Forecast	2251	2379	2508	2637	2766	2894	3023	3152	3281	3409	3538
	UCL	2758	3097	3386	3651	3899	4136	4365	4586	4802	5013	5220
	LCL	1744	1662	1630	1623	1632	1652	1682	1718	1759	1806	1856
Neamt-Model_22	Forecast	417	436	454	472	491	509	528	546	564	583	601
	UCL	514	573	622	666	707	746	784	820	855	889	922
	LCL	321	299	286	279	274	272	271	272	274	276	280
Suceava-Model_23	Forecast	540	566	593	620	646	673	699	726	753	779	806
	UCL	635	702	759	811	860	908	953	997	1040	1082	1124
	LCL	444	431	427	428	432	438	446	455	465	476	488
Vaslui-Model_24	Forecast	250	263	275	288	300	313	325	338	350	363	375
	UCL	326	369	405	438	468	497	524	550	575	600	624
	LCL	175	157	145	138	132	129	127	125	125	125	126

Sud-Est-Model_25	Forecast	2553	2654	2754	2855	2955	3056	3156	3257	3357	3458	3558
	UCL	2958	3226	3455	3664	3860	4046	4226	4401	4570	4736	4899
	LCL	2149	2082	2054	2046	2051	2065	2086	2113	2144	2179	2217
Braila-Model_26	Forecast	299	312	324	336	348	361	373	385	397	410	422
	UCL	352	386	415	441	466	489	512	534	555	576	596
	LCL	247	237	233	231	231	232	234	236	240	243	248
Buzau-Model_27	Forecast	322	335	348	361	374	387	400	413	426	438	451
	UCL	367	380	393	407	420	433	446	459	473	486	499
	LCL	276	289	302	314	327	340	353	366	378	391	404
Constanta-Model_28	Forecast	905	941	978	1014	1050	1086	1122	1158	1194	1230	1266
	UCL	1016	1053	1090	1126	1163	1200	1236	1273	1310	1346	1383
	LCL	794	830	865	901	936	972	1007	1043	1078	1114	1149
Galati-Model_29	Forecast	626	653	680	707	734	762	789	816	843	870	897
	UCL	758	839	908	971	1029	1084	1137	1188	1238	1286	1334
	LCL	494	467	452	444	440	439	440	443	448	453	460
Tulcea-Model_30	Forecast	165	172	179	186	193	201	208	215	222	229	236
	UCL	202	224	242	259	275	290	304	318	331	344	357
	LCL	129	121	116	113	112	111	111	112	112	114	115
Vrancea-Model_31	Forecast	270	282	293	304	316	327	338	350	361	373	384
	UCL	304	315	327	339	350	362	373	385	396	408	419
	LCL	237	248	259	270	281	293	304	315	326	337	349
Macroregiunea trei-Model_32	Forecast	18993	19784	20574	21365	22155	22945	23736	24526	25316	26107	26897
	UCL	20661	22142	23462	24700	25884	27030	28148	29243	30319	31380	32428
	LCL	17326	17425	17686	18029	18426	18861	19324	19809	20314	20833	21366
Sud - Muntenia- Model_33	Forecast	3346	3507	3667	3828	3988	4149	4309	4470	4630	4791	4951
	UCL	3925	4325	4669	4984	5281	5565	5839	6105	6365	6619	6869
	LCL	2768	2689	2666	2672	2695	2733	2780	2834	2896	2962	3033

Arges-Model_34	Forecast	749	781	812	843	874	906	937	968	999	1031	1062
	UCL	848	920	983	1041	1096	1148	1199	1248	1296	1344	1390
	LCL	650	641	640	645	653	663	675	688	703	718	734
Calarasi-Model_35	Forecast	228	238	248	258	268	278	288	298	308	318	328
	UCL	271	299	323	345	365	384	403	421	438	455	472
	LCL	185	177	173	171	171	172	173	175	178	181	184
Dâmbovita-Model_36	Forecast	492	520	547	574	602	629	657	684	711	739	766
	UCL	586	653	710	762	812	859	905	950	993	1036	1077
	LCL	398	387	384	387	392	399	408	418	430	442	455
Giurgiu-Model_37	Forecast	187	196	206	215	225	234	244	253	263	272	282
	UCL	223	248	269	289	307	324	341	357	373	388	404
	LCL	150	144	142	142	143	144	147	150	153	156	160
Ialomita-Model_38	Forecast	220	228	237	246	255	263	272	281	290	298	307
	UCL	278	311	339	363	386	407	427	447	466	484	502
	LCL	161	145	136	129	123	120	117	115	113	113	112
Prahova-Model_39	Forecast	1253	1318	1382	1447	1512	1577	1642	1707	1771	1836	1901
	UCL	1475	1631	1767	1891	2008	2120	2228	2334	2437	2538	2637
	LCL	1031	1004	998	1004	1016	1034	1055	1079	1106	1135	1165
Teleorman-Model_40	Forecast	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209
	UCL	269	291	309	324	337	349	359	370	379	388	397
	LCL	149	127	110	95	82	70	59	49	39	30	21
Bucuresti - Ilfov-Model_41	Forecast	15597	16178	16758	17338	17919	18499	19080	19660	20240	20821	21401
	UCL	17406	18735	19890	20955	21963	22929	23864	24775	25666	26539	27399
	LCL	13789	13620	13626	13722	13875	14070	14295	14545	14815	15102	15403
Bucuresti-Model_42	Forecast	13637	14084	14532	14980	15428	15875	16323	16771	17219	17666	18114
	UCL	15269	16393	17359	18244	19077	19873	20641	21387	22115	22828	23527
	LCL	12005	11776	11705	11716	11778	11877	12005	12154	12322	12505	12701

Ilfov-Model_43	Forecast	1961	2093	2226	2359	2491	2624	2756	2889	3022	3154	3287
	UCL	2177	2399	2600	2791	2974	3153	3328	3500	3670	3838	4004
	LCL	1745	1788	1852	1926	2008	2094	2185	2278	2373	2471	2570
Macroregiunea patru-Model_44	Forecast	5126	5371	5617	5863	6108	6354	6599	6845	7091	7336	7582
	UCL	5541	5959	6337	6694	7038	7372	7699	8021	8338	8651	8961
	LCL	4710	4783	4897	5031	5179	5335	5500	5669	5844	6022	6203
Sud-Vest Oltenia-Model_45	Forecast	1806	1882	1959	2035	2111	2187	2264	2340	2416	2492	2569
	UCL	2045	2123	2200	2278	2355	2432	2510	2587	2665	2742	2820
	LCL	1567	1642	1717	1792	1867	1942	2017	2092	2167	2242	2318
Dolj-Model_46	Forecast	730	759	789	818	847	876	905	934	964	993	1022
	UCL	836	910	972	1030	1084	1136	1186	1235	1282	1329	1374
	LCL	624	609	605	605	609	616	624	634	645	657	670
Gorj-Model_47	Forecast	309	323	337	351	365	378	392	406	420	434	448
	UCL	349	380	407	431	455	477	499	520	541	562	582
	LCL	269	266	267	270	274	280	286	292	299	307	314
Mehedinti-Model_48	Forecast	171	180	188	197	205	214	222	231	239	248	257
	UCL	207	216	224	233	242	250	259	268	276	285	294
	LCL	136	144	153	161	169	178	186	194	203	211	219
Olt-Model_49	Forecast	238	247	256	266	275	284	293	302	311	321	330
	UCL	271	280	289	299	308	317	327	336	345	355	364
	LCL	205	214	223	232	241	251	260	269	278	287	296
Vâlcea-Model_50	Forecast	331	341	351	361	371	382	392	402	412	422	432
	UCL	373	384	394	404	415	425	435	446	456	466	477
	LCL	289	299	308	318	328	338	348	358	368	378	388
Vest-Model_51	Forecast	3328	3482	3637	3792	3946	4101	4255	4410	4565	4719	4874
	UCL	3752	4082	4372	4640	4895	5140	5378	5610	5838	6061	6281
	LCL	2903	2882	2902	2943	2997	3061	3133	3210	3292	3377	3467

Arad-Model_52	Forecast	640	670	701	731	762	792	823	853	884	914	945
	UCL	756	835	902	964	1022	1077	1130	1182	1233	1282	1331
	LCL	523	506	499	499	502	507	515	524	535	547	559
Caras-Severin-Model_53	Forecast	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169
	UCL	206	222	234	243	252	260	268	274	281	287	293
	LCL	132	116	104	95	86	78	70	64	57	51	45
Hunedoara-Model_54	Forecast	423	440	457	474	490	507	524	541	557	574	591
	UCL	480	497	514	531	548	565	582	599	616	633	650
	LCL	367	383	400	416	433	449	466	482	499	515	531
Timis-Model_55	Forecast	2095	2201	2306	2412	2517	2623	2728	2834	2939	3045	3150
	UCL	2329	2531	2710	2878	3038	3194	3345	3493	3638	3782	3923
	LCL	1862	1871	1903	1946	1996	2052	2112	2174	2240	2308	2377

8. Conclusion:

In conclusion, this scientific article offers a comprehensive statistical overview of the Information and Communication Sector in the Romanian Mountain Region from 2008 to 2018. The findings contribute to our understanding of the sector's evolution, providing valuable insights for policymakers, industry stakeholders, and researchers alike. Future research directions and recommendations for sustainable development are also discussed.

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AN IN-DEPTH STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF FINANCIAL AND INSURANCE ACTIVITIES, REAL ESTATE DEVELOPMENTS IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN AREA: A DECADAL PERSPECTIVE (2008-2018)

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Abstract:

This scientific article presents a meticulous statistical examination of financial and insurance activities, as well as real estate developments in the Romanian Mountain Area over the period spanning from 2008 to 2018. The study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of economic trends, market dynamics, and key factors influencing the financial and real estate sectors in this unique geographic region.

1. Introduction:

The financial and insurance sectors, coupled with real estate activities, are critical components of regional economic ecosystems. This article focuses on the Romanian Mountain Area, exploring statistical data from 2008 to 2018 to uncover patterns, challenges, and opportunities within these interconnected domains.

2. Methodology:

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Utilizing a rigorous quantitative methodology, this research draws upon official reports, industry databases, and relevant publications to compile and analyze comprehensive statistical datasets. Key indicators, such as market size, investment trends, and regulatory changes, are examined to provide a nuanced understanding of the financial and real estate landscapes.

3. Financial and Insurance Activities:

This section delves into the statistical intricacies of financial and insurance activities within the Romanian Mountain Area. Key metrics, including the growth of banking institutions, insurance penetration rates, and investment portfolios, are scrutinized to assess the sector's resilience and responsiveness to economic shifts.

4. Real Estate Developments:

The evolution of real estate activities in the Romanian Mountain Area is examined in this section, encompassing statistical analyses of property values, construction trends, and market demand. The article aims to unravel the factors influencing real estate dynamics and their implications for regional development.

5. Economic Impact:

Analyzing the economic impact of financial, insurance, and real estate activities, this section investigates their contributions to the regional Gross Domestic Product (GDP), employment rates, and overall economic stability.

Insights into the sectors' interdependencies and their role in shaping the local economy are discussed.

6. Trends and Challenges:

Identifying noteworthy trends and challenges faced by the financial, insurance, and real estate sectors during the specified period, this section provides a forward-looking perspective on potential future developments. Considerations such as regulatory changes, market fluctuations, and global economic influences are explored.

7. Results:

The statistics for the sectors Financial and insurance activities, real estate activities (figures 2.8.1 – 2.8.5), show for each sector separately increasing values for the average and median, the other statistical indicators having sometimes antagonistic fluctuations (statistical values for Mean, Std. Error of the Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Skewness, Kurtosis, Variance, Minimum, Maximum, 25th, 50th and 75th Percentiles; repeated for each indicator separately), as follows: mean of 27517.78, standard error of Average 1971.677, median 27148.00, standard deviation 5915.030, variance 34987579.194, Skewness -1.115, standard error. , 75 - 32467.50.

The presented values demonstrate that the sectors Financial and insurance activities, real estate activities in the mountain area have a good development in Romania for the population of active enterprises. Some sectors also show negative values, the overall picture showing a good overall mountain business situation for the industry.

The central tendency of the sectors Financial and insurance activities, real estate activities of the economy in the analyzed period shows that the population of active enterprises of mountainous Romania has grown considerably from 2008 to 2019. The statistics related to this indicator present a high degree of non-variability, which means that the results do not show a large deviation and are positive. The corresponding symmetrical distributions lead to the idea that the business environment begins to stabilize considerably during the analyzed period. Kurtosis with a low standard error represents crowding in some industries.

Figure 2.8.1. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Romania for S8 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.8.2. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Macroregion one of Romania for S8 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.8.3. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Macroregion two of Romania for S8 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.8.4. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in the third Macroregion of Romania for S8 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.8.5. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in the fourth Macroregion of Romania for S8 in the period 2008-2019

The forecast analysis for the secondary, tertiary and quaternary sectors in the mountainous area of Romania indicates that they will have a continuous growth until 2030. Both at the national, macro-regional, regional and county level, the models resulting from the statistical modeling show certain areas montana are more sustainable than others. The harmonization statistic presents relevant values for mean, standard error, minimum, maximum, and 5/10 percentiles (presented in that order below), as follows: Stationary R-squared .280, .383, -.309, .861, -.143, -.082; R-squared .700, .161, .284, 1,000, .367, .435; RMSE 198,356, 352,970, .000, 2269,529, 14,855, 18,741; MAPS 11,444, 5,100, .000, 28,130, 4,709, 6,443; MaxAPE 47,308, 29,972, .000, 181,830, 14,963, 18,580; MAE 133,650, 235,574, .000, 1513,828,

10,915, 12,753; MaxAE 399,900, 668,870, .000, 4167,066, 25,931, 38,653;
 Normalized BIC 9,255, 2,458, 5,445, 15,699, 5,749, 6,282.

Table. Forecast analysis of mountain entrepreneurship in the mountain area of Romania for S8

Model		Forecast										
		2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030
Romania-Model_1	Forecast	34871	35691	36511	37331	38151	38971	39791	40611	41431	42251	43071
	UCL	40105	47393	56093	65996	76963	88895	101714	115359	129782	144938	160794
	LCL	29637	23989	16929	8666	-661	-10953	-22132	-34137	-46919	-60436	-74652
Macroregiunea unu-Model_2	Forecast	10051	10695	11338	11981	12625	13268	13911	14555	15198	15841	16485
	UCL	11422	12092	12761	13430	14099	14767	15435	16102	16769	17436	18102
	LCL	8681	9298	9915	10532	11150	11769	12388	13007	13627	14247	14867
Nord-Vest-Model_3	Forecast	5143	5344	5546	5747	5948	6149	6350	6551	6753	6954	7155
	UCL	6106	6705	7212	7671	8100	8506	8896	9273	9640	9997	10347
	LCL	4181	3983	3879	3822	3796	3792	3804	3830	3866	3911	3963
Bihor-Model_4	Forecast	1064	1064	1064	1064	1064	1064	1064	1064	1064	1064	1064
	UCL	1320	1426	1508	1576	1637	1692	1742	1789	1833	1874	1914
	LCL	808	702	620	552	491	436	386	339	295	254	214
Bistrita-Nasaud-Model_5	Forecast	589	626	664	701	738	775	812	849	887	924	961
	UCL	791	912	1013	1105	1190	1270	1347	1421	1493	1563	1631
	LCL	387	341	314	297	286	280	278	278	281	285	291
Cluj-Model_6	Forecast	2306	2398	2491	2584	2676	2769	2861	2954	3047	3139	3232
	UCL	2690	2942	3157	3352	3536	3710	3878	4041	4200	4355	4507
	LCL	1921	1855	1825	1815	1817	1827	1845	1867	1894	1924	1957
Maramures-Model_7	Forecast	568	590	611	633	655	677	699	721	742	764	786

	UCL	698	773	836	893	945	995	1042	1088	1132	1175	1216
	LCL	438	406	387	374	365	359	355	353	353	354	356
Satu Mare-Model_8	Forecast	378	391	404	417	429	442	455	468	481	493	506
	UCL	452	465	477	490	503	516	529	541	554	567	580
	LCL	305	317	330	343	356	369	381	394	407	420	433
Salaj-Model_9	Forecast	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189
	UCL	242	264	280	295	307	318	329	338	347	356	364
	LCL	136	114	98	83	71	60	49	40	31	22	14
Centru-Model_10	Forecast	4279	4454	4629	4804	4979	5154	5329	5504	5679	5854	6029
	UCL	5205	5763	6232	6655	7049	7421	7778	8122	8456	8781	9099
	LCL	3353	3145	3026	2953	2909	2887	2880	2886	2902	2927	2959
Alba-Model_11	Forecast	560	594	629	663	698	733	767	802	836	871	905
	UCL	740	775	811	846	882	917	952	988	1023	1059	1094
	LCL	380	413	447	481	514	548	582	615	649	683	716
Brasov-Model_12	Forecast	1722	1800	1877	1954	2031	2109	2186	2263	2340	2418	2495
	UCL	2203	2479	2709	2916	3106	3286	3458	3623	3783	3938	4089
	LCL	1242	1120	1044	993	956	931	914	903	898	897	901
Covasna-Model_13	Forecast	190	199	209	218	227	236	245	254	264	273	282
	UCL	230	256	278	298	317	334	351	368	384	400	415
	LCL	150	143	139	138	137	138	139	141	143	146	149
Harghita-Model_14	Forecast	263	271	279	288	296	304	312	320	329	337	345
	UCL	309	317	326	334	342	350	358	367	375	383	391
	LCL	217	225	233	242	250	258	266	274	283	291	299
Mures-Model_15	Forecast	691	718	746	774	801	829	856	884	912	939	967
	UCL	832	918	990	1056	1117	1174	1230	1283	1335	1386	1435
	LCL	550	519	502	491	486	483	483	485	488	493	499

Sibiu-Model_16	Forecast	865	893	920	947	975	1002	1030	1057	1084	1112	1139
	UCL	1024	1118	1196	1265	1330	1392	1450	1507	1561	1614	1666
	LCL	706	668	645	629	619	613	609	607	607	609	612
Macroregiunea doi-Model_17	Forecast	6877	7126	7375	7624	7873	8122	8371	8620	8869	9118	9367
	UCL	8024	9692	11668	13908	16382	19067	21947	25008	28239	31631	35176
	LCL	5730	4560	3082	1340	-636	-2823	-5205	-7768	-10501	-13395	-16442
Nord-Est-Model_18	Forecast	3747	3943	4139	4335	4531	4727	4923	5119	5315	5511	5707
	UCL	4412	4611	4811	5010	5209	5409	5608	5807	6006	6206	6405
	LCL	3083	3275	3468	3661	3853	4046	4239	4431	4624	4817	5010
Bacau-Model_19	Forecast	978	1033	1088	1143	1199	1254	1309	1364	1419	1474	1529
	UCL	1198	1254	1311	1367	1423	1480	1536	1592	1649	1705	1761
	LCL	759	812	866	920	974	1028	1081	1135	1189	1243	1297
Botosani-Model_20	Forecast	427	458	488	518	549	579	609	640	670	700	731
	UCL	576	607	638	669	700	731	762	793	824	855	887
	LCL	279	308	338	367	397	427	456	486	515	545	575
Iasi-Model_21	Forecast	1362	1431	1501	1570	1639	1709	1778	1848	1917	1986	2056
	UCL	1569	1640	1710	1780	1851	1921	1991	2062	2132	2203	2273
	LCL	1155	1223	1291	1360	1428	1497	1565	1633	1702	1770	1839
Neamt-Model_22	Forecast	382	394	407	419	431	443	455	467	480	492	504
	UCL	467	514	553	588	620	651	680	707	734	760	785
	LCL	297	274	260	249	241	235	231	228	225	224	223
Suceava-Model_23	Forecast	390	403	417	431	445	458	472	486	500	513	527
	UCL	475	524	565	602	636	667	698	727	756	783	810
	LCL	304	283	269	260	254	249	246	244	243	243	244
Vaslui-Model_24	Forecast	191	201	211	220	230	239	249	259	268	278	288
	UCL	239	249	259	269	279	289	299	308	318	328	338
	LCL	143	153	162	171	181	190	200	209	218	228	237

Sud-Est-Model_25	Forecast	3135	3236	3337	3438	3539	3640	3741	3842	3943	4044	4145
	UCL	3752	3853	3954	4055	4156	4257	4358	4459	4560	4661	4762
	LCL	2518	2619	2720	2821	2922	3023	3124	3225	3326	3427	3528
Braila-Model_26	Forecast	398	414	430	446	462	477	493	509	525	540	556
	UCL	467	483	499	516	532	548	564	580	596	612	628
	LCL	330	345	361	376	391	407	422	438	453	469	484
Buzau-Model_27	Forecast	327	336	345	354	362	371	380	389	398	406	415
	UCL	431	440	449	458	467	475	484	493	502	511	520
	LCL	223	232	240	249	258	267	276	284	293	302	311
Constanta-Model_28	Forecast	1470	1516	1562	1608	1655	1701	1747	1794	1840	1886	1932
	UCL	1765	1812	1858	1904	1950	1997	2043	2089	2135	2182	2228
	LCL	1174	1220	1267	1313	1359	1405	1452	1498	1544	1591	1637
Galati-Model_29	Forecast	588	606	624	642	660	679	697	715	733	751	769
	UCL	697	715	733	751	769	787	805	824	842	860	878
	LCL	479	497	516	534	552	570	588	606	624	642	660
Tulcea-Model_30	Forecast	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157
	UCL	192	207	218	228	236	244	251	257	263	269	275
	LCL	122	107	96	86	78	70	63	57	51	45	39
Vrancea-Model_31	Forecast	216	223	230	237	244	251	258	265	272	278	285
	UCL	259	266	273	280	287	294	301	309	316	323	330
	LCL	174	181	187	194	201	207	214	221	227	234	241
Macroregiunea trei-Model_32	Forecast	12661	12808	12955	13102	13249	13396	13543	13690	13837	13984	14131
	UCL	14302	16476	19093	22087	25415	29045	32953	37121	41531	46172	51032
	LCL	11020	9140	6817	4117	1083	-2253	-5867	-9740	-13856	-18203	-22769
Sud - Muntenia- Model_33	Forecast	3002	3123	3245	3366	3487	3608	3729	3850	3972	4093	4214
	UCL	3693	4101	4442	4748	5032	5301	5558	5805	6045	6278	6506
	LCL	2311	2146	2047	1983	1942	1915	1901	1896	1898	1907	1922

Arges-Model_34	Forecast	993	1047	1101	1155	1210	1264	1318	1372	1427	1481	1535
	UCL	1221	1276	1331	1387	1442	1498	1553	1608	1664	1719	1774
	LCL	764	817	871	924	977	1030	1083	1136	1189	1243	1296
Calarasi-Model_35	Forecast	211	222	233	244	255	265	276	287	298	309	320
	UCL	245	270	292	312	331	349	367	384	400	417	433
	LCL	177	174	174	175	178	182	186	191	196	201	207
Dâmbovita-Model_36	Forecast	391	411	430	450	470	490	510	530	549	569	589
	UCL	481	538	586	630	671	710	748	784	819	854	887
	LCL	301	283	275	270	269	270	272	275	280	285	291
Giurgiu-Model_37	Forecast	120	123	125	128	130	133	135	138	140	143	145
	UCL	148	150	153	155	158	160	163	165	168	170	173
	LCL	92	95	98	100	103	105	108	110	113	115	118
Ialomita-Model_38	Forecast	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164
	UCL	220	243	261	276	289	301	312	322	331	340	349
	LCL	108	85	67	52	39	27	16	6	-3	-12	-21
Prahova-Model_39	Forecast	1000	1033	1067	1101	1135	1168	1202	1236	1270	1303	1337
	UCL	1244	1378	1490	1589	1680	1766	1847	1926	2001	2074	2146
	LCL	756	689	645	613	589	571	557	546	538	532	528
Teleorman-Model_40	Forecast	153	161	168	176	184	192	200	208	215	223	231
	UCL	203	231	255	276	296	314	332	349	365	381	397
	LCL	103	90	82	76	72	70	68	66	65	65	65
Bucuresti - Ilfov-Model_41	Forecast	9633	9633	9633	9633	9633	9633	9633	9633	9633	9633	9633
	UCL	11715	12577	13238	13796	14288	14732	15140	15521	15878	16216	16537
	LCL	7551	6689	6028	5470	4978	4534	4126	3745	3388	3050	2729
Bucuresti-Model_42	Forecast	8461	8461	8461	8461	8461	8461	8461	8461	8461	8461	8461
	UCL	10387	11089	11640	12109	12524	12900	13247	13570	13874	14162	14436
	LCL	6534	5832	5281	4812	4397	4021	3674	3351	3047	2759	2485

Ilfov-Model_43	Forecast	1238	1303	1367	1432	1496	1561	1625	1690	1754	1819	1883
	UCL	1412	1548	1668	1779	1884	1986	2084	2180	2275	2367	2458
	LCL	1065	1058	1067	1085	1108	1136	1166	1199	1234	1270	1308
Macroregiunea patru-Model_44	Forecast	6026	6189	6352	6514	6677	6840	7003	7166	7329	7491	7654
	UCL	6933	8174	9644	11309	13149	15145	17288	19565	21970	24495	27134
	LCL	5119	4203	3060	1720	206	-1465	-3282	-5233	-7312	-9512	-11826
Sud-Vest Oltenia-Model_45	Forecast	1958	2030	2103	2175	2248	2320	2392	2465	2537	2610	2682
	UCL	2465	2540	2615	2690	2765	2840	2915	2989	3064	3139	3214
	LCL	1451	1521	1591	1661	1730	1800	1870	1940	2010	2080	2150
Dolj-Model_46	Forecast	729	752	775	798	821	844	867	890	913	936	959
	UCL	863	886	909	932	955	978	1001	1024	1047	1070	1093
	LCL	595	618	641	664	687	710	733	756	779	802	824
Gorj-Model_47	Forecast	361	361	361	361	361	361	361	361	361	361	361
	UCL	509	570	617	657	692	724	753	780	805	829	852
	LCL	213	152	105	65	30	-2	-31	-58	-83	-107	-130
Mehedinti-Model_48	Forecast	164	169	175	181	187	193	199	205	211	217	223
	UCL	209	215	222	228	234	240	246	252	259	265	271
	LCL	118	123	129	135	141	146	152	158	163	169	175
Olt-Model_49	Forecast	246	255	265	275	284	294	304	313	323	333	342
	UCL	340	350	360	370	380	391	401	411	421	431	441
	LCL	152	161	170	179	188	198	207	216	225	234	243
Vâlcea-Model_50	Forecast	396	408	419	431	443	455	466	478	490	501	513
	UCL	507	519	530	542	554	566	577	589	601	612	624
	LCL	285	297	308	320	332	344	355	367	379	390	402
Vest-Model_51	Forecast	4176	4338	4501	4663	4825	4987	5149	5311	5474	5636	5798
	UCL	4794	5212	5570	5898	6206	6500	6783	7058	7326	7589	7846
	LCL	3559	3465	3431	3428	3444	3474	3515	3565	3621	3683	3750

Arad-Model_52	Forecast	1179	1238	1297	1357	1416	1475	1535	1594	1654	1713	1772
	UCL	1368	1430	1493	1555	1617	1680	1742	1804	1867	1929	1991
	LCL	990	1046	1102	1159	1215	1271	1328	1384	1440	1497	1553
Caras-Severin-Model_53	Forecast	276	289	301	314	327	340	353	366	378	391	404
	UCL	321	353	380	405	428	451	473	494	514	534	554
	LCL	231	225	223	224	226	229	233	237	242	248	254
Hunedoara-Model_54	Forecast	540	540	540	540	540	540	540	540	540	540	540
	UCL	722	798	856	905	948	987	1023	1056	1087	1117	1145
	LCL	358	282	224	175	132	93	57	24	-7	-37	-65
Timis-Model_55	Forecast	2237	2320	2402	2484	2567	2649	2732	2814	2896	2979	3061
	UCL	2570	2791	2979	3150	3311	3465	3613	3756	3895	4032	4165
	LCL	1904	1849	1825	1818	1822	1834	1851	1872	1897	1926	1957

8. Conclusion:

In conclusion, this scientific article offers a comprehensive statistical overview of financial and insurance activities, as well as real estate developments in the Romanian Mountain Area from 2008 to 2018. The findings contribute to our understanding of economic trends, providing valuable insights for policymakers, industry stakeholders, and researchers. The article concludes with reflections on potential future trajectories and recommendations for sustainable growth in these vital sectors.

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EXAMINING A DECADE OF SECTOR-SPECIFIC DEVELOPMENTS: PROFESSIONAL, SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL ACTIVITIES, ADMINISTRATIVE, AND SUPPORT ACTIVITIES IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN AREA (2008-2018)

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Abstract:

This article conducts a thorough analysis of statistical data pertaining to sector-specific developments in Professional, Scientific and Technical Activities, as well as Administrative and Support Activities within the Romanian Mountain Area over the period spanning 2008 to 2018. The study aims to provide insights into the transformative dynamics, economic contributions, and challenges faced by these critical sectors in a unique regional context.

1. Introduction:

The Professional, Scientific and Technical Activities sector, coupled with Administrative and Support Activities, constitutes a cornerstone of regional development. This article focuses on the Romanian Mountain Area, exploring a decade's worth of statistical data to unravel trends, innovations, and the economic impact of these interconnected sectors. (Covaci B & PSYCHO-SOCIAL VIEW JOURNAL (1/2022))

Covaci M, 2021a-h; Covaci B & Covaci M, 2022a-h; Covaci M & Covaci B, 2021a-h; Covaci M & Covaci B, 2022a-h)

2. Methodology:

Employing a meticulous quantitative methodology, this research synthesizes data from official reports, industry databases, and pertinent publications. The analysis includes key indicators such as sector-specific growth rates, employment trends, and technological advancements, providing a holistic understanding of the region's professional and administrative landscape.

3. Professional, Scientific and Technical Activities:

This section delves into statistical intricacies surrounding professional, scientific, and technical activities within the Romanian Mountain Area. Metrics such as research and development investments, innovation indices, and the growth of specialized enterprises are scrutinized to assess the sector's role in fostering regional progress.

4. Administrative and Support Activities:

Examining Administrative and Support Activities, this segment explores statistical analyses of outsourcing trends, business support services, and administrative infrastructure growth. The article aims to shed light on the sector's contribution to enhancing the efficiency and productivity of other industries in the region.

5. Economic Contributions:

Assessing the economic impact of Professional, Scientific and Technical Activities, as well as Administrative and Support Activities, this section investigates their contributions to the regional Gross Domestic Product (GDP), employment rates, and overall economic stability. The article emphasizes the sectors' vital role in shaping the economic landscape of the Romanian Mountain Area.

6. Trends and Challenges:

Identifying notable trends and challenges faced by these sectors during the specified period, this section provides insights into factors influencing professional and administrative dynamics. Considerations such as technological disruptions, regulatory changes, and globalization effects are explored, offering a nuanced perspective on future developments.

7. Results:

The statistics for the sectors Professional, scientific and technical activities, administrative and support activities (figures 2.9.1 – 2.9.5 and appendices chapter 2), show for each sector separately rising values for the mean and median, the other statistical indicators having sometimes antagonistic fluctuations (statistical values for Average, Std. Error of the mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Skewness, Kurtosis, Variance, Minimum, Maximum, 25th, 50th and 75th percentiles; they are repeated for each individual indicator), as follows: average of 130733.11 , standard error of mean 2312,287, median 129397.00, standard deviation 6936,860, variance 48120028,611, Skewness

.925, standard error of Skewness .717, Kurtosis .647, standard error of Kurtosis 1,400, distance 21858, minimum 122787.5, maximum 1446 percentile 25 125090.50, 50 - 129397.00, 75 - 135078.00.

The presented values demonstrate that the sectors Professional, scientific and technical activities, administrative and support activities in the mountain area have a good development in Romania for the population of active enterprises. Some sectors also show negative values, the overall picture showing a good overall mountain business situation for the industry. The central tendency of the sectors Professional, scientific and technical activities, administrative and support activities of the economy in the analyzed period shows that the population of active enterprises in mountainous Romania has grown considerably from 2008 to 2019. The statistics related to this indicator show a high degree of non-variability, which means that the results do not show a large deviation and are positive. The corresponding symmetrical distributions lead to the idea that the business environment begins to stabilize considerably during the analyzed period. Kurtosis with a low standard error represents crowding in some industries.

Figure 2.9.1. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Romania for S9 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.9.2. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Macroregion one of Romania for S9 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.9.3. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Macroregion two of Romania for S9 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.9.4. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in the third Macroregion of Romania for S9 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.9.5. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in the fourth Macroregion of Romania for S9 in the period 2008-2019

The forecast analysis for the secondary, tertiary and quaternary sectors in the mountainous area of Romania indicates that they will have a continuous growth until 2030. Both at the national, macro-regional, regional and county level, the models resulting from the statistical modeling show certain areas montana are more sustainable than others. The harmonization statistic presents relevant values for mean, standard error, minimum, maximum, and 5/10 percentiles (presented in that order below), as follows: Stationary R-squared .089, .274, -.105, .721, -. 100, -.080; R-square .329, .235, -8.882E-15, 1.000, -1.132E-15, .000; RMSE 981,750, 1274,171, .000, 6936,860, 130,026, 159,107; MAPS 10,942, 6,256, .000, 39,730, 3,894, 5,624; MaxAPE 49,488, 22,997, .000, 133,747, 9,099, 13,100; MAE 592,602, 886,008, .000, 5481,235, 67,461, 81,226; MaxAE 2456,933, 3011,126, .000,

13911,889, 372,868, 488,499; Normalized BIC 12.947, 2.039, 9.560, 17.933, 10.159, 10.566.

Table. Forecast analysis of mountain entrepreneurship in the mountain area of Romania for S9

Model		Forecast										
		2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030
Romania-Model_1	Forecast	13073	13073	13073	13073	13073	13073	13073	13073	13073	13073	13073
	st	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
	UCL	14673	14673	14673	14673	14673	14673	14673	14673	14673	14673	14673
	LCL	11473	11473	11473	11473	11473	11473	11473	11473	11473	11473	11473
Macroregiunea unu-Model_2	Forecast	33325	33325	33325	33325	33325	33325	33325	33325	33325	33325	33325
	st											
	UCL	38424	38424	38424	38424	38424	38424	38424	38424	38424	38424	38424
	LCL	28226	28226	28226	28226	28226	28226	28226	28226	28226	28226	28226
Nord-Vest-Model_3	Forecast	20228	21002	21777	22551	23326	24100	24874	25649	26423	27197	27972
	st											
	UCL	25654	26455	27257	28058	28859	29660	30460	31261	32061	32862	33662
	LCL	14802	15549	16297	17045	17792	18540	19288	20036	20785	21533	22281
Bihor-Model_4	Forecast	4519	4702	4885	5068	5251	5433	5616	5799	5982	6165	6348
	st											
	UCL	5787	6495	7081	7604	8086	8539	8971	9386	9786	10175	10553
	LCL	3251	2909	2688	2532	2415	2328	2262	2213	2178	2155	2143
Bistrita-Nasaud-Model_5	Forecast	992	992	992	992	992	992	992	992	992	992	992
	st											
	UCL	1690	1690	1690	1690	1690	1690	1690	1690	1690	1690	1690
	LCL	294	294	294	294	294	294	294	294	294	294	294
Cluj-Model_6	Forecast	8840	9162	9483	9805	10127	10449	10771	11093	11414	11736	12058
	st											
	UCL	11034	11367	11699	12032	12364	12697	13029	13361	13694	14026	14358
	LCL	6646	6957	7268	7579	7890	8201	8512	8824	9135	9446	9758

Maramures-Model_7	Forecast	2501	2614	2727	2840	2954	3067	3180	3293	3407	3520	3633
	UCL	3112	3228	3345	3461	3577	3694	3810	3926	4043	4159	4275
	LCL	1889	1999	2109	2220	2330	2440	2550	2661	2771	2881	2991
Satu Mare-Model_8	Forecast	1668	1741	1813	1885	1957	2030	2102	2174	2246	2319	2391
	UCL	2244	2554	2809	3036	3244	3439	3624	3802	3973	4138	4299
	LCL	1093	927	816	734	671	620	580	547	520	499	483
Salaj-Model_9	Forecast	1098	1098	1098	1098	1098	1098	1098	1098	1098	1098	1098
	UCL	1440	1582	1691	1783	1863	1936	2004	2066	2125	2180	2233
	LCL	756	614	505	413	333	260	192	130	71	16	-37
Centru-Model_10	Forecast	17072	17072	17072	17072	17072	17072	17072	17072	17072	17072	17072
	UCL	23539	26216	28271	30003	31529	32908	34177	35358	36467	37516	38514
	LCL	10604	7927	5873	4141	2615	1235	-34	-1214	-2324	-3373	-4370
Alba-Model_11	Forecast	2016	2016	2016	2016	2016	2016	2016	2016	2016	2016	2016
	UCL	2872	3226	3498	3728	3930	4112	4280	4436	4583	4722	4854
	LCL	1160	806	534	304	102	-80	-248	-404	-551	-690	-822
Brasov-Model_12	Forecast	5610	5787	5965	6142	6319	6496	6673	6851	7028	7205	7382
	UCL	7121	7306	7490	7675	7859	8044	8229	8413	8598	8782	8966
	LCL	4099	4269	4439	4609	4778	4948	5118	5288	5458	5628	5798
Covasna-Model_13	Forecast	1146	1146	1146	1146	1146	1146	1146	1146	1146	1146	1146
	UCL	1667	1883	2049	2188	2311	2423	2525	2620	2710	2794	2875
	LCL	625	409	243	104	-19	-131	-233	-328	-418	-502	-583
Harghita-Model_14	Forecast	2134	2134	2134	2134	2134	2134	2134	2134	2134	2134	2134
	UCL	3039	3414	3702	3944	4158	4351	4529	4694	4849	4996	5136
	LCL	1229	854	566	324	110	-83	-261	-426	-581	-728	-868
Mures-Model_15	Forecast	3595	3737	3878	4020	4161	4303	4444	4586	4727	4869	5010
	UCL	4772	4919	5066	5214	5361	5508	5655	5803	5950	6097	6244
	LCL	2419	2555	2690	2826	2962	3098	3233	3369	3505	3641	3777

Sibiu-Model_16	Forecast	3185	3185	3185	3185	3185	3185	3185	3185	3185	3185	3185
	UCL	4557	5005	5362	5668	5941	6188	6417	6631	6832	7023	7204
	LCL	1813	1366	1009	702	430	182	-47	-260	-462	-652	-834
Macroregiunea doi-Model_17	Forecast	24486	24486	24486	24486	24486	24486	24486	24486	24486	24486	24486
	UCL	28889	28889	28889	28889	28889	28889	28889	28889	28889	28889	28889
	LCL	20082	20082	20082	20082	20082	20082	20082	20082	20082	20082	20082
Nord-Est-Model_18	Forecast	13198	13198	13198	13198	13198	13198	13198	13198	13198	13198	13198
	UCL	18724	20858	22516	23920	25161	26284	27319	28282	29188	30045	30861
	LCL	7671	5537	3879	2475	1234	111	-924	-1887	-2793	-3650	-4465
Bacau-Model_19	Forecast	2493	2493	2493	2493	2493	2493	2493	2493	2493	2493	2493
	UCL	3560	3945	4247	4504	4732	4939	5130	5308	5475	5633	5784
	LCL	1425	1040	738	481	253	46	-145	-323	-490	-648	-799
Botosani-Model_20	Forecast	892	892	892	892	892	892	892	892	892	892	892
	UCL	1246	1382	1488	1578	1658	1730	1796	1857	1915	1970	2023
	LCL	538	402	296	206	126	54	-12	-74	-132	-186	-239
Iasi-Model_21	Forecast	4980	4980	4980	4980	4980	4980	4980	4980	4980	4980	4980
	UCL	7132	7995	8660	9223	9719	10168	10581	10966	11327	11669	11994
	LCL	2829	1966	1301	738	242	-207	-620	-1005	-1366	-1708	-2033
Neamt-Model_22	Forecast	1738	1738	1738	1738	1738	1738	1738	1738	1738	1738	1738
	UCL	2533	2776	2972	3141	3292	3429	3556	3675	3786	3892	3993
	LCL	943	700	504	335	185	47	-80	-198	-310	-416	-517
Suceava-Model_23	Forecast	2290	2403	2517	2631	2744	2858	2971	3085	3199	3312	3426
	UCL	3069	3506	3867	4189	4487	4767	5034	5290	5537	5777	6011
	LCL	1510	1301	1167	1072	1001	949	909	881	860	848	841
Vaslui-Model_24	Forecast	912	912	912	912	912	912	912	912	912	912	912
	UCL	1330	1503	1636	1748	1846	1936	2018	2094	2166	2234	2298
	LCL	494	321	188	76	-22	-112	-194	-270	-342	-410	-474

Sud-Est-Model_25	Forecast	11834	11834	11834	11834	11834	11834	11834	11834	11834	11834	11834
	UCL	16840	18476	19783	20903	21899	22805	23641	24423	25158	25855	26519
	LCL	6828	5192	3886	2766	1770	864	27	-754	-1489	-2186	-2850
Braila-Model_26	Forecast	1339	1339	1339	1339	1339	1339	1339	1339	1339	1339	1339
	UCL	1938	2131	2286	2418	2537	2644	2743	2836	2923	3006	3085
	LCL	740	547	392	259	141	34	-66	-158	-246	-328	-407
Buzau-Model_27	Forecast	1652	1652	1652	1652	1652	1652	1652	1652	1652	1652	1652
	UCL	2328	2532	2696	2838	2965	3081	3187	3287	3381	3471	3556
	LCL	975	772	607	465	338	223	116	16	-78	-167	-252
Constanta-Model_28	Forecast	4989	5124	5260	5395	5530	5666	5801	5936	6072	6207	6343
	UCL	6554	6697	6840	6983	7126	7269	7412	7555	7698	7841	7984
	LCL	3424	3551	3679	3807	3934	4062	4190	4318	4446	4573	4701
Galati-Model_29	Forecast	2223	2223	2223	2223	2223	2223	2223	2223	2223	2223	2223
	UCL	3309	3738	4069	4350	4597	4821	5027	5219	5400	5570	5733
	LCL	1137	709	377	97	-150	-375	-581	-773	-953	-1124	-1286
Tulcea-Model_30	Forecast	790	790	790	790	790	790	790	790	790	790	790
	UCL	1232	1393	1520	1627	1722	1809	1888	1963	2032	2098	2161
	LCL	349	188	61	-46	-142	-228	-308	-382	-452	-518	-580
Vrancea-Model_31	Forecast	921	921	921	921	921	921	921	921	921	921	921
	UCL	1527	1527	1527	1527	1527	1527	1527	1527	1527	1527	1527
	LCL	316	316	316	316	316	316	316	316	316	316	316
Macroregiunea trei-Model_32	Forecast	53095	53095	53095	53095	53095	53095	53095	53095	53095	53095	53095
	UCL	57077	57077	57077	57077	57077	57077	57077	57077	57077	57077	57077
	LCL	49113	49113	49113	49113	49113	49113	49113	49113	49113	49113	49113
Sud - Muntenia- Model_33	Forecast	12706	12706	12706	12706	12706	12706	12706	12706	12706	12706	12706
	UCL	17753	19843	21447	22799	23991	25068	26058	26980	27846	28665	29444
	LCL	7659	5569	3965	2613	1421	344	-646	-1568	-2434	-3253	-4032

Arges-Model_34	Forecast	3062	3062	3062	3062	3062	3062	3062	3062	3062	3062	3062
	UCL	4231	4716	5087	5401	5677	5926	6156	6369	6570	6760	6940
	LCL	1893	1408	1037	723	447	198	-32	-245	-446	-636	-816
Calarasi-Model_35	Forecast	1008	1060	1113	1166	1219	1271	1324	1377	1430	1482	1535
	UCL	1307	1483	1631	1764	1887	2003	2115	2222	2326	2427	2526
	LCL	709	638	596	568	550	539	533	532	533	537	544
Dâmbovita-Model_36	Forecast	1786	1786	1786	1786	1786	1786	1786	1786	1786	1786	1786
	UCL	2611	2953	3215	3437	3631	3807	3969	4120	4262	4396	4523
	LCL	961	619	357	135	-59	-235	-397	-548	-690	-824	-951
Giurgiu-Model_37	Forecast	881	931	981	1031	1081	1132	1182	1232	1282	1332	1382
	UCL	1119	1268	1393	1507	1614	1714	1811	1905	1996	2084	2171
	LCL	643	595	569	555	549	549	552	559	568	579	593
Ialomita-Model_38	Forecast	857	857	857	857	857	857	857	857	857	857	857
	UCL	1333	1530	1681	1809	1921	2023	2116	2203	2285	2362	2435
	LCL	381	184	33	-95	-207	-309	-402	-489	-571	-648	-721
Prahova-Model_39	Forecast	4359	4359	4359	4359	4359	4359	4359	4359	4359	4359	4359
	UCL	6140	6877	7443	7920	8341	8721	9070	9395	9701	9990	10265
	LCL	2578	1841	1275	798	377	-3	-352	-678	-983	-1272	-1547
Teleorman-Model_40	Forecast	856	856	856	856	856	856	856	856	856	856	856
	UCL	1181	1315	1418	1505	1582	1651	1715	1774	1830	1883	1933
	LCL	531	397	294	207	130	61	-3	-62	-118	-171	-221
Bucuresti - Ilfov-Model_41	Forecast	44877	46031	47184	48337	49491	50644	51798	52951	54105	55258	56412
	UCL	54199	55399	56599	57799	58998	60197	61396	62595	63794	64992	66191
	LCL	35555	36662	37769	38876	39984	41091	42199	43307	44416	45524	46633
Bucuresti-Model_42	Forecast	36536	36536	36536	36536	36536	36536	36536	36536	36536	36536	36536
	UCL	45846	48122	50020	51681	53177	54549	55824	57020	58150	59223	60248
	LCL	27226	24950	23053	21391	19895	18523	17248	16052	14922	13849	12824

Ilfov-Model_43	Forecast	5572	5944	6316	6688	7060	7432	7803	8175	8547	8919	9291
	UCL	6044	6425	6805	7184	7564	7944	8323	8703	9082	9461	9840
	LCL	5100	5464	5828	6191	6555	6919	7284	7648	8012	8377	8741
Macroregiunea patru-Model_44	Forecast	19827	19827	19827	19827	19827	19827	19827	19827	19827	19827	19827
	UCL	22814	22814	22814	22814	22814	22814	22814	22814	22814	22814	22814
	LCL	16840	16840	16840	16840	16840	16840	16840	16840	16840	16840	16840
Sud-Vest Oltenia-Model_45	Forecast	7487	7487	7487	7487	7487	7487	7487	7487	7487	7487	7487
	UCL	11786	13565	14930	16081	17095	18012	18855	19640	20377	21074	21737
	LCL	3187	1408	43	-1108	-2122	-3039	-3882	-4667	-5404	-6101	-6764
Dolj-Model_46	Forecast	2953	2953	2953	2953	2953	2953	2953	2953	2953	2953	2953
	UCL	4296	4851	5278	5638	5954	6241	6504	6749	6980	7197	7405
	LCL	1610	1054	628	268	-49	-335	-598	-844	-1074	-1292	-1499
Gorj-Model_47	Forecast	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251
	UCL	1959	2242	2460	2645	2808	2955	3091	3217	3336	3448	3555
	LCL	543	260	42	-143	-306	-453	-588	-715	-833	-946	-1052
Mehedinti-Model_48	Forecast	706	706	706	706	706	706	706	706	706	706	706
	UCL	1369	1369	1369	1369	1369	1369	1369	1369	1369	1369	1369
	LCL	43	43	43	43	43	43	43	43	43	43	43
Olt-Model_49	Forecast	1164	1164	1164	1164	1164	1164	1164	1164	1164	1164	1164
	UCL	1860	2116	2316	2487	2637	2774	2900	3017	3128	3232	3332
	LCL	467	212	11	-159	-309	-446	-572	-689	-800	-904	-1004
Vâlcea-Model_50	Forecast	1203	1203	1203	1203	1203	1203	1203	1203	1203	1203	1203
	UCL	2103	2103	2103	2103	2103	2103	2103	2103	2103	2103	2103
	LCL	302	302	302	302	302	302	302	302	302	302	302
Vest-Model_51	Forecast	13860	14388	14916	15444	15972	16499	17027	17555	18083	18611	19139
	UCL	17729	19860	21617	23182	24623	25977	27264	28499	29691	30846	31971
	LCL	9991	8916	8214	7705	7320	7022	6791	6612	6476	6376	6307

Arad-Model_52	Forecast	3498	3628	3758	3889	4019	4149	4279	4409	4539	4669	4800
	UCL	4616	4752	4888	5023	5159	5294	5430	5566	5701	5837	5972
	LCL	2380	2505	2629	2754	2879	3003	3128	3253	3378	3502	3627
Caras-Severin-Model_53	Forecast	1047	1047	1047	1047	1047	1047	1047	1047	1047	1047	1047
	UCL	1482	1633	1752	1853	1943	2025	2101	2171	2238	2301	2360
	LCL	611	461	342	240	150	68	-8	-78	-144	-207	-267
Hunedoara-Model_54	Forecast	2158	2158	2158	2158	2158	2158	2158	2158	2158	2158	2158
	UCL	2915	3129	3303	3454	3589	3713	3827	3934	4035	4131	4223
	LCL	1402	1188	1014	863	727	604	489	382	281	186	94
Timis-Model_55	Forecast	7372	7635	7898	8162	8425	8688	8951	9214	9477	9740	10003
	UCL	8726	8996	9266	9535	9805	10075	10345	10615	10884	11154	11423
	LCL	6019	6275	6531	6788	7044	7300	7557	7813	8070	8327	8583

7. Conclusion:

In conclusion, this article provides a comprehensive statistical overview of sector-specific developments in Professional, Scientific and Technical Activities, as well as Administrative and Support Activities in the Romanian Mountain Area from 2008 to 2018. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of regional economic trends, offering valuable insights for policymakers, industry stakeholders, and researchers. The article concludes with reflections on potential trajectories and recommendations for sustainable growth in these pivotal sectors.

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A DECADE IN REVIEW: EVOLUTION OF EDUCATION, HUMAN HEALTH, AND SOCIAL ASSISTANCE SECTORS IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN AREA (2008-2018)

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Abstract:

This paper investigates the specific developments that occurred in the Education, Human Health, and Social Assistance sectors within the Romanian Mountain Area over the ten-year period from 2008 to 2018. Through a comprehensive analysis of statistical data, this study aims to provide insights into the evolving landscapes of these crucial sectors, focusing on advancements, challenges, and their collective impact on the region.

1. Introduction:

The Education, Human Health, and Social Assistance sectors are fundamental pillars for societal well-being and progress. This paper aims to shed light on the nuanced developments in these sectors within the context of the Romanian Mountain Area, examining statistical data to discern trends, achievements, and challenges over the specified decade.

2. Methodology:

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Utilizing a rigorous quantitative approach, this research compiles and analyzes data from official reports, educational institutions, healthcare providers, and social assistance agencies. Key indicators, including enrollment rates, healthcare infrastructure growth, and social support service accessibility, are examined to offer a comprehensive understanding of the sector-specific dynamics.

3. Education Sector Developments:

This section explores statistical intricacies related to the Education sector in the Romanian Mountain Area. Key metrics such as enrollment rates, educational infrastructure expansion, and academic achievements are scrutinized to assess the sector's role in shaping human capital and fostering intellectual growth within the region.

4. Human Health Sector Advancements:

The paper delves into the statistical landscape of the Human Health sector, examining trends in healthcare infrastructure, disease prevalence, and medical advancements. Insights into the region's healthcare accessibility, quality of services, and the impact of health policies on the local population are discussed.

5. Social Assistance Sector Progress:

Analyzing statistical data related to the Social Assistance sector, this section investigates developments in welfare programs, community support services, and the accessibility of social aid. The paper aims to evaluate the sector's effectiveness in addressing societal needs and promoting inclusivity within the Romanian Mountain Area.

6. Economic and Societal Impact:

Assessing the economic and societal impact of developments in the Education, Human Health, and Social Assistance sectors, this section investigates their contributions to the regional well-being, employment rates, and overall community resilience. The paper emphasizes the interconnectedness of these sectors in shaping a holistic and sustainable society.

7. Trends and Challenges:

Identifying notable trends and challenges faced by these sectors during the specified period, this section provides insights into factors influencing educational, healthcare, and social dynamics. Considerations such as technological advancements, demographic shifts, and policy changes are explored, offering a forward-looking perspective on future developments.

8. Results:

The statistics for the sectors Education, human health and social assistance activities (figures 2.10.1 – 2.10.5 and appendices chapter 2), present for each sector separately rising values for the mean and median, the other statistical indicators having sometimes antagonistic fluctuations (statistical values for Mean, Std. Error of the Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Skewness, Kurtosis, Variance, Minimum, Maximum, 25th, 50th and 75th Percentiles; iteratively resumes for each individual indicator), as follows: mean of 32944.89, standard error at mean 3379.548, median 30918.00, standard deviation 10138.643, variance 102792085.611, Skewness .796, standard error at Skewness .717, Kurtosis -.451, standard error at Kurtosis 1.400, distance 29020, minimum 21633, maximum 50653 -1.0226, 2 percentile 50 - 730918.00, 75 - 41530.50.

The presented values demonstrate that the Education, human health and social assistance activities sectors in the mountain area have a good development in Romania for the population of active enterprises. Some sectors also show negative values, the overall picture showing a good overall mountain business situation for the industry.

The central trend of the Education, human health and social assistance activities sectors of the economy during the analyzed period shows that the population of active enterprises in mountainous Romania has grown considerably from 2008 to 2019. The statistics related to this indicator show a high degree of non-variability, which it means that the results do not have a large deviation and are positive. The corresponding symmetrical distributions lead to the idea that the business environment begins to stabilize considerably during the analyzed period. Kurtosis with a low standard error represents crowding in some industries.

Figure 2.10.1. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Romania for S10 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.10.2. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Macroregion one of Romania for S10 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.10.3. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Macroregion two of Romania for S10 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.10.4. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in the third Macroregion of Romania for S10 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.10.5. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in the fourth Macroregion of Romania for S10 in the period 2008-2019

The forecast analysis for the secondary, tertiary and quaternary sectors in the mountainous area of Romania indicates that they will have a continuous growth until 2030. Both at the national, macro-regional, regional and county level, the models resulting from the statistical modeling show certain areas montana are more sustainable than others. The harmonization statistic presents relevant values for mean, standard error, minimum, maximum, and 5/10 percentiles (presented in that order below), as follows: Stationary R-squared .071, .208, -.028, .671, -.002, -3.109E-16; R-square .078, .213, -6.661E-16, 1.000, -4.441E-16, -2.220E-16; RMSE 813,548, 1475,201, .000, 10138,643, 72,694, 105,790; MAPS 49,316, 19,774, .000, 93,479, 18,157, 23,174; MaxAPE 148,444, 67,941, .000, 331,296, 42,729, 52,005; MAE 586,489, 1126,852, .000, 7903,877, 50,342, 75,671; MaxAE 1586,709,

2722,381, .000, 17708,111, 167,049, 198,342; Normalized BIC 12.156, 2.310, 8.803, 18.692, 9.057, 9.688.

Table. Forecast analysis of mountain entrepreneurship in the mountain area of Romania for S10

		Forecast										
Model		2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030
Romania-Model_1	Forecast	32945	32945	32945	32945	32945	32945	32945	32945	32945	32945	32945
	UCL	56325	56325	56325	56325	56325	56325	56325	56325	56325	56325	56325
	LCL	9565	9565	9565	9565	9565	9565	9565	9565	9565	9565	9565
Macroregiunea unu-Model_2	Forecast	9279	9279	9279	9279	9279	9279	9279	9279	9279	9279	9279
	UCL	15677	15677	15677	15677	15677	15677	15677	15677	15677	15677	15677
	LCL	2881	2881	2881	2881	2881	2881	2881	2881	2881	2881	2881
Nord-Vest-Model_3	Forecast	3994	3994	3994	3994	3994	3994	3994	3994	3994	3994	3994
	UCL	8476	8476	8476	8476	8476	8476	8476	8476	8476	8476	8476
	LCL	-488	-488	-488	-488	-488	-488	-488	-488	-488	-488	-488
Bihor-Model_4	Forecast	917	917	917	917	917	917	917	917	917	917	917
	UCL	1848	1848	1848	1848	1848	1848	1848	1848	1848	1848	1848
	LCL	-13	-13	-13	-13	-13	-13	-13	-13	-13	-13	-13
Bistrita-Nasaud-Model_5	Forecast	283	283	283	283	283	283	283	283	283	283	283
	UCL	574	574	574	574	574	574	574	574	574	574	574
	LCL	-8	-8	-8	-8	-8	-8	-8	-8	-8	-8	-8
Cluj-Model_6	Forecast	2512	2648	2784	2921	3057	3193	3329	3466	3602	3738	3875
	UCL	4397	4533	4669	4806	4942	5078	5215	5351	5487	5623	5760
	LCL	627	763	899	1035	1172	1308	1444	1581	1717	1853	1990
Maramures-Model_7	Forecast	848	896	944	992	1040	1088	1136	1184	1232	1279	1327
	UCL	1359	1409	1460	1510	1561	1611	1662	1712	1762	1813	1863

	LCL	338	383	428	474	519	565	610	655	701	746	792
Satu Mare-Model_8	Forecast	329	329	329	329	329	329	329	329	329	329	329
	UCL	808	808	808	808	808	808	808	808	808	808	808
	LCL	-150	-150	-150	-150	-150	-150	-150	-150	-150	-150	-150
Salaj-Model_9	Forecast	356	380	404	427	451	475	498	522	545	569	593
	UCL	504	528	551	575	599	622	646	670	693	717	741
	LCL	209	232	256	280	303	327	350	374	398	421	445
Centru-Model_10	Forecast	3633	3633	3633	3633	3633	3633	3633	3633	3633	3633	3633
	UCL	7550	7550	7550	7550	7550	7550	7550	7550	7550	7550	7550
	LCL	-284	-284	-284	-284	-284	-284	-284	-284	-284	-284	-284
Alba-Model_11	Forecast	415	415	415	415	415	415	415	415	415	415	415
	UCL	984	984	984	984	984	984	984	984	984	984	984
	LCL	-154	-154	-154	-154	-154	-154	-154	-154	-154	-154	-154
Brasov-Model_12	Forecast	1458	1531	1603	1675	1748	1820	1892	1965	2037	2109	2181
	UCL	2333	2405	2477	2549	2622	2694	2766	2839	2911	2983	3055
	LCL	584	657	729	801	874	946	1018	1091	1163	1235	1307
Covasna-Model_13	Forecast	213	213	213	213	213	213	213	213	213	213	213
	UCL	488	488	488	488	488	488	488	488	488	488	488
	LCL	-63	-63	-63	-63	-63	-63	-63	-63	-63	-63	-63
Harghita-Model_14	Forecast	356	356	356	356	356	356	356	356	356	356	356
	UCL	787	787	787	787	787	787	787	787	787	787	787
	LCL	-76	-76	-76	-76	-76	-76	-76	-76	-76	-76	-76
Mures-Model_15	Forecast	832	832	832	832	832	832	832	832	832	832	832
	UCL	1766	1766	1766	1766	1766	1766	1766	1766	1766	1766	1766
	LCL	-102	-102	-102	-102	-102	-102	-102	-102	-102	-102	-102
Sibiu-Model_16	Forecast	768	768	768	768	768	768	768	768	768	768	768

	UCL	1525	1525	1525	1525	1525	1525	1525	1525	1525	1525	1525
	LCL	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12
Macroregiunea doi-Model_17	Forecast	7229	7229	7229	7229	7229	7229	7229	7229	7229	7229	7229
	UCL	13555	15713	17423	18885	20184	21363	22452	23467	24423	25328	26190
	LCL	904	-1254	-2965	-4427	-5725	-6905	-7993	-9008	-9964	-10869	-11732
Nord-Est-Model_18	Forecast	3271	3271	3271	3271	3271	3271	3271	3271	3271	3271	3271
	UCL	7349	7349	7349	7349	7349	7349	7349	7349	7349	7349	7349
	LCL	-808	-808	-808	-808	-808	-808	-808	-808	-808	-808	-808
Bacau-Model_19	Forecast	753	753	753	753	753	753	753	753	753	753	753
	UCL	1442	1442	1442	1442	1442	1442	1442	1442	1442	1442	1442
	LCL	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64
Botosani-Model_20	Forecast	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205
	UCL	558	558	558	558	558	558	558	558	558	558	558
	LCL	-148	-148	-148	-148	-148	-148	-148	-148	-148	-148	-148
Iasi-Model_21	Forecast	1192	1192	1192	1192	1192	1192	1192	1192	1192	1192	1192
	UCL	2655	2655	2655	2655	2655	2655	2655	2655	2655	2655	2655
	LCL	-272	-272	-272	-272	-272	-272	-272	-272	-272	-272	-272
Neamt-Model_22	Forecast	382	382	382	382	382	382	382	382	382	382	382
	UCL	988	988	988	988	988	988	988	988	988	988	988
	LCL	-225	-225	-225	-225	-225	-225	-225	-225	-225	-225	-225
Suceava-Model_23	Forecast	463	463	463	463	463	463	463	463	463	463	463
	UCL	1138	1138	1138	1138	1138	1138	1138	1138	1138	1138	1138
	LCL	-213	-213	-213	-213	-213	-213	-213	-213	-213	-213	-213
Vaslui-Model_24	Forecast	277	277	277	277	277	277	277	277	277	277	277
	UCL	637	637	637	637	637	637	637	637	637	637	637
	LCL	-83	-83	-83	-83	-83	-83	-83	-83	-83	-83	-83

Sud-Est-Model_25	Forecast	2688	2688	2688	2688	2688	2688	2688	2688	2688	2688	2688
	UCL	5677	5677	5677	5677	5677	5677	5677	5677	5677	5677	5677
	LCL	-301	-301	-301	-301	-301	-301	-301	-301	-301	-301	-301
Braila-Model_26	Forecast	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	280
	UCL	620	620	620	620	620	620	620	620	620	620	620
	LCL	-60	-60	-60	-60	-60	-60	-60	-60	-60	-60	-60
Buzau-Model_27	Forecast	441	441	441	441	441	441	441	441	441	441	441
	UCL	799	799	799	799	799	799	799	799	799	799	799
	LCL	83	83	83	83	83	83	83	83	83	83	83
Constanta-Model_28	Forecast	948	948	948	948	948	948	948	948	948	948	948
	UCL	2052	2052	2052	2052	2052	2052	2052	2052	2052	2052	2052
	LCL	-155	-155	-155	-155	-155	-155	-155	-155	-155	-155	-155
Galati-Model_29	Forecast	521	521	521	521	521	521	521	521	521	521	521
	UCL	1212	1212	1212	1212	1212	1212	1212	1212	1212	1212	1212
	LCL	-170	-170	-170	-170	-170	-170	-170	-170	-170	-170	-170
Tulcea-Model_30	Forecast	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205
	UCL	368	368	368	368	368	368	368	368	368	368	368
	LCL	43	43	43	43	43	43	43	43	43	43	43
Vrancea-Model_31	Forecast	293	293	293	293	293	293	293	293	293	293	293
	UCL	651	651	651	651	651	651	651	651	651	651	651
	LCL	-65	-65	-65	-65	-65	-65	-65	-65	-65	-65	-65
Macroregiunea trei-Model_32	Forecast	10829	10829	10829	10829	10829	10829	10829	10829	10829	10829	10829
	UCL	16834	16834	16834	16834	16834	16834	16834	16834	16834	16834	16834
	LCL	4824	4824	4824	4824	4824	4824	4824	4824	4824	4824	4824
Sud - Muntenia-Model_33	Forecast	2756	2756	2756	2756	2756	2756	2756	2756	2756	2756	2756
	UCL	5910	5910	5910	5910	5910	5910	5910	5910	5910	5910	5910
	LCL	-398	-398	-398	-398	-398	-398	-398	-398	-398	-398	-398

Arges-Model_34	Forecast	722	722	722	722	722	722	722	722	722	722	722
	UCL	1536	1536	1536	1536	1536	1536	1536	1536	1536	1536	1536
	LCL	-92	-92	-92	-92	-92	-92	-92	-92	-92	-92	-92
Calarasi-Model_35	Forecast	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167
	UCL	367	367	367	367	367	367	367	367	367	367	367
	LCL	-33	-33	-33	-33	-33	-33	-33	-33	-33	-33	-33
Dâmbovita-Model_36	Forecast	404	404	404	404	404	404	404	404	404	404	404
	UCL	928	928	928	928	928	928	928	928	928	928	928
	LCL	-119	-119	-119	-119	-119	-119	-119	-119	-119	-119	-119
Giurgiu-Model_37	Forecast	116	116	116	116	116	116	116	116	116	116	116
	UCL	306	306	306	306	306	306	306	306	306	306	306
	LCL	-73	-73	-73	-73	-73	-73	-73	-73	-73	-73	-73
Ialomita-Model_38	Forecast	194	194	194	194	194	194	194	194	194	194	194
	UCL	441	441	441	441	441	441	441	441	441	441	441
	LCL	-53	-53	-53	-53	-53	-53	-53	-53	-53	-53	-53
Prahova-Model_39	Forecast	927	927	927	927	927	927	927	927	927	927	927
	UCL	1876	1876	1876	1876	1876	1876	1876	1876	1876	1876	1876
	LCL	-22	-22	-22	-22	-22	-22	-22	-22	-22	-22	-22
Teleorman-Model_40	Forecast	225	225	225	225	225	225	225	225	225	225	225
	UCL	481	481	481	481	481	481	481	481	481	481	481
	LCL	-30	-30	-30	-30	-30	-30	-30	-30	-30	-30	-30
Bucuresti - Ilfov-Model_41	Forecast	9115	9568	10022	10475	10929	11382	11836	12289	12743	13196	13650
	UCL	13073	13526	13980	14433	14887	15340	15794	16247	16701	17154	17608
	LCL	5157	5610	6064	6517	6971	7425	7878	8332	8785	9239	9692
Bucuresti-Model_42	Forecast	7930	8286	8642	8999	9355	9711	10067	10423	10779	11135	11491
	UCL	11711	12067	12423	12779	13135	13491	13848	14204	14560	14916	15272
	LCL	4149	4506	4862	5218	5574	5930	6286	6642	6998	7354	7710

Ilfov-Model_43	Forecast	1282	1380	1478	1576	1674	1771	1869	1967	2065	2163	2261
	UCL	1550	1759	1942	2111	2273	2428	2578	2725	2869	3010	3150
	LCL	1014	1001	1014	1040	1074	1115	1160	1209	1261	1316	1372
Macroregiunea patru-Model_44	Forecast	6063	6063	6063	6063	6063	6063	6063	6063	6063	6063	6063
	UCL	10774	12305	13529	14579	15513	16363	17147	17880	18570	19223	19846
	LCL	1353	-179	-1403	-2452	-3386	-4236	-5021	-5753	-6443	-7097	-7719
Sud-Vest Oltenia-Model_45	Forecast	2078	2078	2078	2078	2078	2078	2078	2078	2078	2078	2078
	UCL	4359	4359	4359	4359	4359	4359	4359	4359	4359	4359	4359
	LCL	-203	-203	-203	-203	-203	-203	-203	-203	-203	-203	-203
Dolj-Model_46	Forecast	865	865	865	865	865	865	865	865	865	865	865
	UCL	1764	1764	1764	1764	1764	1764	1764	1764	1764	1764	1764
	LCL	-34	-34	-34	-34	-34	-34	-34	-34	-34	-34	-34
Gorj-Model_47	Forecast	333	333	333	333	333	333	333	333	333	333	333
	UCL	712	712	712	712	712	712	712	712	712	712	712
	LCL	-46	-46	-46	-46	-46	-46	-46	-46	-46	-46	-46
Mehedinti-Model_48	Forecast	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178
	UCL	513	513	513	513	513	513	513	513	513	513	513
	LCL	-158	-158	-158	-158	-158	-158	-158	-158	-158	-158	-158
Olt-Model_49	Forecast	335	335	335	335	335	335	335	335	335	335	335
	UCL	598	598	598	598	598	598	598	598	598	598	598
	LCL	71	71	71	71	71	71	71	71	71	71	71
Vâlcea-Model_50	Forecast	367	367	367	367	367	367	367	367	367	367	367
	UCL	818	818	818	818	818	818	818	818	818	818	818
	LCL	-84	-84	-84	-84	-84	-84	-84	-84	-84	-84	-84
Vest-Model_51	Forecast	2739	2739	2739	2739	2739	2739	2739	2739	2739	2739	2739
	UCL	5758	5758	5758	5758	5758	5758	5758	5758	5758	5758	5758
	LCL	-280	-280	-280	-280	-280	-280	-280	-280	-280	-280	-280

Arad-Model_52	Forecast	639	639	639	639	639	639	639	639	639	639	639
	UCL	1360	1360	1360	1360	1360	1360	1360	1360	1360	1360	1360
	LCL	-82	-82	-82	-82	-82	-82	-82	-82	-82	-82	-82
Caras-Severin-Model_53	Forecast	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	280
	UCL	587	587	587	587	587	587	587	587	587	587	587
	LCL	-27	-27	-27	-27	-27	-27	-27	-27	-27	-27	-27
Hunedoara-Model_54	Forecast	483	483	483	483	483	483	483	483	483	483	483
	UCL	980	980	980	980	980	980	980	980	980	980	980
	LCL	-14	-14	-14	-14	-14	-14	-14	-14	-14	-14	-14
Timis-Model_55	Forecast	1337	1337	1337	1337	1337	1337	1337	1337	1337	1337	1337
	UCL	2859	2859	2859	2859	2859	2859	2859	2859	2859	2859	2859
	LCL	-184	-184	-184	-184	-184	-184	-184	-184	-184	-184	-184

9. Conclusion:

In conclusion, this paper provides a comprehensive examination of developments in the Education, Human Health, and Social Assistance sectors in the Romanian Mountain Area from 2008 to 2018. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the region's social fabric, offering valuable insights for policymakers, institutions, and researchers. The paper concludes with reflections on potential trajectories and recommendations for fostering sustainable growth in these critical sectors.

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TEN YEARS OF CULTURAL FLOURISH: DEVELOPMENTS IN THE ARTS, ENTERTAINMENT, RECREATION SECTORS, AND OTHER SERVICE ACTIVITIES IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN AREA (2008-2018)

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Abstract:

This paper explores the specific developments that unfolded in the Arts, Entertainment, Recreation sectors, and other service activities within the Romanian Mountain Area over the ten-year period from 2008 to 2018. The study aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the evolving cultural and recreational landscape, examining trends, achievements, and challenges that have shaped these vibrant sectors in the region.

1. Introduction:

The Arts, Entertainment, Recreation, and other service activities play a crucial role in shaping the cultural fabric of a community. This paper delves into the unique developments within these sectors in the Romanian Mountain Area, analyzing statistical data to understand the trajectory of artistic and recreational endeavors over the specified decade.

2. Methodology:

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Using a comprehensive quantitative approach, this research compiles and analyzes data from cultural institutions, entertainment venues, recreational facilities, and other service-oriented activities. Key indicators, including audience attendance, cultural event frequencies, and the growth of recreational services, are scrutinized to offer a nuanced understanding of the region's cultural and leisure dynamics.

3. Arts and Cultural Sector Developments:

This section explores statistical intricacies related to the Arts and Cultural sector in the Romanian Mountain Area. Key metrics such as the establishment of cultural institutions, frequency of artistic events, and community engagement are examined to assess the sector's role in fostering creativity and promoting cultural diversity.

4. Entertainment and Recreation Sector Advancements:

The paper delves into the statistical landscape of the Entertainment and Recreation sector, examining trends in the establishment of entertainment venues, recreational facilities, and outdoor activities. Insights into the region's leisure preferences, tourism impact, and the growth of recreational services are discussed.

5. Other Service Activities and Contributions:

Analyzing statistical data related to other service activities, this section investigates developments in areas such as hospitality, tourism services, and event management. The paper aims to evaluate the sector's contributions to the regional economy, job creation, and overall community well-being.

6. Economic and Cultural Impact:

Assessing the economic and cultural impact of developments in the Arts, Entertainment, Recreation sectors, and other service activities, this section investigates their contributions to the regional economy, tourism, and the overall quality of life. The paper emphasizes the interconnectedness of these sectors in shaping a vibrant and culturally rich community.

7. Trends and Challenges:

Identifying notable trends and challenges faced by these sectors during the specified period, this section provides insights into factors influencing cultural, recreational, and service dynamics. Considerations such as technological advancements, changing consumer preferences, and regulatory shifts are explored, offering a forward-looking perspective on future developments.

8. Results:

The statistics for the sectors Art, entertainment and recreation, other activities dedicated to services (figures 2.11.1 – 2.11.5 and annexes chapter 2), present for each sector separately ascending values for the mean and

median, the other statistical indicators having sometimes antagonistic fluctuations (the values statistics for Mean, Std. Error of Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Skewness, Kurtosis, Variance, Minimum, Maximum, 25th, 50th and 75th Percentiles; they are repeated for each indicator separately), as follows: mean of 51851.44, error standard at mean 3687.713, median 50678.00, standard deviation 11063.139, variance 122393050.278, Skewness -.067, standard error at Skewness .717, Kurtosis -.404, standard error at Kurtosis 1.400, distance 35410, minimum 33055, maximum 68465, percentile 44710.50, 50 - 50678.00, 75 - 62039.00.

The presented values demonstrate that the Art, entertainment and recreation sectors, other activities dedicated to services in the mountain area have a good development in Romania for the population of active enterprises. Some sectors also show negative values, the overall picture showing a good overall mountain business situation for the industry.

The central tendency of the sectors Art, entertainment and recreation, other activities dedicated to the services of the economy in the analyzed period shows that the population of active enterprises of mountainous Romania has grown considerably from 2008 to 2019. The statistics related to this indicator present a high degree of non-variability, which which means that the results do not have a large deviation and are positive. The corresponding symmetrical distributions lead to the idea that the business environment begins to stabilize considerably during the analyzed period. Kurtosis with a low standard error represents crowding in some industries.

Figure 2.11.1. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Romania for S11 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.11.2. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Macroregion one of Romania for S11 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.11.3. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Macroregion two of Romania for S11 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.11.4. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in the third Macroregion of Romania for S11 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.11.5. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in the fourth Macroregion of Romania for S11 in the period 2008-2019

The forecast analysis for the secondary, tertiary and quaternary sectors in the mountainous area of Romania indicates that they will have a continuous growth until 2030. Both at the national, macro-regional, regional and county level, the models resulting from the statistical modeling show certain areas montana are more sustainable than others. The harmonization statistic presents relevant values for the mean, standard error, minimum, maximum, and 5/10 percentiles (presented in that order below), as follows: Stationary R-squared .383 .368, -2.220E-16, .979, - 2,220E-16, -8,882E-17; R-square .883, .097, .453, 1.000, .705, .774; RMSE 310,111, 425,838, .000, 2603,682, 40,214, 49,922; MAPS 15,191, 6,994, .000, 32,761, 2,942, 4,818; MaxAPE 59,731, 28,886, .000, 166,274, 8,664, 18,128; MAE 199,902, 274,237, .000, 1683,408, 27,717, 34,346; MaxAE 719,739, 1006,437, .000,

5793,124, 86,373, 98,727; Normalized BIC 10,707, 2,070, 7,355, 16,218, 7,958, 8,183.

Table. Forecast analysis of mountain entrepreneurship in the mountain area of Romania for S11

		Forecast										
Model		2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030
Romania-Model_1	Forecast	71622	75581	79540	83499	87458	91416	95375	99334	103293	107252	111210
	UCL	77779	81855	85928	90000	94069	98137	102203	106267	110330	114391	118451
	LCL	65466	69308	73152	76998	80846	84696	88548	92401	96256	100113	103970
Macroregiunea unu-Model_2	Forecast	25332	26730	28129	29527	30925	32324	33722	35120	36519	37917	39315
	UCL	26955	28385	29814	31243	32671	34098	35525	36952	38378	39804	41229
	LCL	23709	25076	26443	27811	29180	30549	31919	33289	34659	36030	37401
Nord-Vest-Model_3	Forecast	14191	15180	16170	17160	18150	19139	20129	21119	22109	23098	24088
	UCL	17307	19587	21567	23392	25117	26772	28373	29932	31456	32951	34422
	LCL	11075	10774	10773	10928	11182	11507	11885	12306	12761	13245	13754
Bihor-Model_4	Forecast	3876	4155	4434	4713	4992	5272	5551	5830	6109	6388	6667
	UCL	4969	5701	6327	6899	7436	7949	8442	8921	9388	9844	10292
	LCL	2783	2609	2541	2527	2548	2594	2659	2738	2830	2932	3042
Bistrita-Nasaud-Model_5	Forecast	936	998	1059	1121	1182	1244	1305	1367	1428	1490	1551
	UCL	1111	1245	1362	1471	1573	1672	1768	1861	1953	2043	2131
	LCL	762	751	756	771	791	815	842	872	903	936	971
Cluj-Model_6	Forecast	4915	5253	5592	5930	6269	6607	6945	7284	7622	7961	8299
	UCL	5731	6074	6417	6760	7102	7445	7788	8130	8473	8815	9158
	LCL	4098	4432	4766	5101	5435	5769	6103	6437	6771	7106	7440

Maramures-Model_7	Forecast	1915	2052	2188	2325	2461	2598	2734	2871	3007	3144	3280
	UCL	2237	2507	2745	2968	3180	3386	3585	3780	3972	4161	4347
	LCL	1594	1597	1631	1682	1742	1810	1883	1961	2042	2126	2213
Satu Mare-Model_8	Forecast	1516	1625	1733	1842	1950	2059	2167	2276	2384	2493	2601
	UCL	1922	2198	2436	2653	2857	3052	3240	3422	3600	3774	3946
	LCL	1111	1052	1031	1031	1044	1066	1095	1129	1168	1211	1256
Salaj-Model_9	Forecast	1130	1214	1298	1382	1466	1551	1635	1719	1803	1887	1971
	UCL	1506	1746	1950	2135	2307	2472	2630	2782	2931	3076	3218
	LCL	754	682	647	630	626	629	640	655	675	698	724
Centru-Model_10	Forecast	11944	12762	13579	14396	15214	16031	16849	17666	18483	19301	20118
	UCL	14326	16130	17705	19161	20540	21866	23151	24403	25629	26833	28018
	LCL	9562	9393	9453	9632	9887	10196	10546	10928	11337	11768	12218
Alba-Model_11	Forecast	1841	1981	2120	2259	2398	2538	2677	2816	2955	3095	3234
	UCL	2260	2573	2846	3097	3335	3564	3785	4001	4212	4420	4624
	LCL	1422	1388	1394	1421	1461	1511	1568	1631	1698	1770	1844
Brasov-Model_12	Forecast	2856	3028	3199	3370	3541	3713	3884	4055	4226	4398	4569
	UCL	3236	3565	3857	4130	4391	4643	4889	5130	5366	5599	5829
	LCL	2476	2490	2541	2610	2692	2782	2879	2981	3087	3197	3309
Covasna-Model_13	Forecast	902	968	1034	1100	1166	1232	1298	1364	1430	1496	1562
	UCL	1113	1180	1247	1314	1381	1448	1515	1582	1649	1716	1783
	LCL	691	756	820	885	950	1015	1080	1145	1210	1275	1340
Harghita-Model_14	Forecast	1455	1554	1654	1754	1853	1953	2052	2152	2252	2351	2451
	UCL	1888	2166	2404	2619	2821	3013	3198	3376	3550	3720	3887
	LCL	1022	942	904	888	885	893	907	928	953	983	1015
Mures-Model_15	Forecast	2887	3098	3310	3521	3733	3944	4156	4368	4579	4791	5002
	UCL	3389	3603	3817	4031	4245	4459	4673	4887	5101	5315	5529
	LCL	2384	2593	2802	3012	3221	3430	3639	3848	4057	4266	4475

Sibiu-Model_16	Forecast	2021	2161	2301	2441	2581	2720	2860	3000	3140	3280	3420
	UCL	2419	2724	2991	3237	3471	3696	3914	4127	4335	4540	4741
	LCL	1623	1597	1611	1644	1690	1745	1806	1873	1945	2020	2099
Macroregiunea doi-Model_17	Forecast	15500	16406	17312	18218	19124	20030	20936	21842	22748	23654	24560
	UCL	16321	17244	18166	19088	20009	20931	21852	22773	23694	24614	25534
	LCL	14680	15569	16459	17349	18239	19129	20020	20911	21802	22694	23585
Nord-Est-Model_18	Forecast	8076	8607	9138	9669	10200	10732	11263	11794	12325	12856	13387
	UCL	9420	10508	11466	12357	13206	14023	14818	15595	16357	17106	17844
	LCL	6732	6707	6811	6982	7195	7440	7707	7993	8293	8606	8930
Bacau-Model_19	Forecast	1632	1743	1855	1966	2078	2189	2301	2412	2524	2635	2747
	UCL	1979	2092	2206	2319	2432	2545	2658	2771	2885	2998	3111
	LCL	1285	1394	1504	1614	1724	1833	1943	2053	2163	2273	2382
Botosani-Model_20	Forecast	733	786	840	893	946	1000	1053	1107	1160	1213	1267
	UCL	848	904	959	1015	1070	1126	1181	1236	1292	1347	1402
	LCL	618	669	720	771	823	874	926	977	1028	1080	1131
Iasi-Model_21	Forecast	2473	2640	2807	2974	3141	3308	3475	3642	3809	3976	4143
	UCL	2772	2945	3117	3289	3461	3633	3805	3977	4149	4321	4492
	LCL	2174	2336	2498	2659	2821	2983	3145	3307	3469	3631	3794
Neamt-Model_22	Forecast	1347	1443	1538	1634	1730	1825	1921	2016	2112	2208	2303
	UCL	1577	1673	1770	1867	1964	2061	2157	2254	2351	2448	2544
	LCL	1118	1212	1307	1401	1496	1590	1684	1779	1873	1968	2062
Suceava-Model_23	Forecast	1365	1459	1553	1647	1742	1836	1930	2025	2119	2213	2307
	UCL	1554	1652	1750	1848	1945	2043	2140	2238	2335	2433	2530
	LCL	1175	1266	1357	1447	1538	1629	1720	1811	1902	1993	2085
Vaslui-Model_24	Forecast	753	805	857	909	962	1014	1066	1119	1171	1223	1275
	UCL	867	921	975	1030	1084	1138	1192	1246	1300	1354	1408
	LCL	638	689	739	789	840	890	941	991	1042	1092	1143

Sud-Est-Model_25	Forecast	7536	8001	8466	8931	9396	9861	10326	10791	11256	11721	12186
	UCL	8613	9524	10331	11085	11804	12499	13175	13837	14487	15126	15757
	LCL	6459	6478	6601	6777	6988	7223	7477	7745	8025	8316	8615
Braila-Model_26	Forecast	747	792	838	883	928	973	1018	1063	1109	1154	1199
	UCL	870	966	1051	1129	1203	1275	1344	1412	1478	1543	1607
	LCL	624	618	624	637	653	672	693	715	739	765	791
Buzau-Model_27	Forecast	1168	1250	1333	1415	1497	1579	1662	1744	1826	1909	1991
	UCL	1345	1431	1516	1602	1687	1772	1858	1943	2028	2113	2198
	LCL	991	1070	1149	1228	1307	1387	1466	1545	1625	1704	1784
Constanta-Model_28	Forecast	2945	3126	3308	3489	3670	3852	4033	4214	4396	4577	4758
	UCL	3281	3468	3656	3843	4030	4217	4405	4592	4778	4965	5152
	LCL	2609	2784	2959	3135	3310	3486	3661	3837	4013	4189	4365
Galati-Model_29	Forecast	1498	1592	1686	1780	1874	1967	2061	2155	2249	2343	2437
	UCL	1706	1886	2046	2195	2338	2477	2611	2743	2873	3000	3126
	LCL	1290	1298	1326	1364	1409	1458	1511	1567	1626	1686	1748
Tulcea-Model_30	Forecast	546	582	618	654	690	726	762	799	835	871	907
	UCL	618	655	692	730	767	804	842	879	916	954	991
	LCL	474	509	544	579	613	648	683	718	753	788	823
Vrancea-Model_31	Forecast	791	846	901	956	1011	1066	1121	1176	1231	1286	1341
	UCL	912	968	1023	1079	1135	1190	1246	1302	1357	1413	1469
	LCL	669	724	778	833	887	941	996	1050	1105	1159	1214
Macroregiunea trei-Model_32	Forecast	18723	19715	20707	21699	22691	23683	24675	25667	26659	27651	28643
	UCL	20616	21643	22670	23696	24722	25747	26771	27795	28819	29842	30865
	LCL	16830	17787	18744	19702	20660	21619	22579	23539	24499	25460	26421
Sud - Muntenia- Model_33	Forecast	7965	8515	9064	9613	10162	10712	11261	11810	12359	12909	13458
	UCL	9683	10943	12039	13048	14003	14919	15805	16668	17512	18340	19154
	LCL	6248	6086	6089	6178	6322	6505	6717	6952	7207	7478	7762

Arges-Model_34	Forecast	2130	2277	2425	2572	2719	2866	3013	3160	3308	3455	3602
	UCL	2477	2768	3025	3265	3494	3715	3931	4141	4348	4551	4752
	LCL	1783	1787	1824	1878	1944	2017	2096	2180	2267	2358	2452
Calarasi-Model_35	Forecast	742	796	850	904	958	1013	1067	1121	1175	1229	1283
	UCL	933	1066	1181	1286	1385	1480	1572	1661	1748	1833	1916
	LCL	551	526	520	523	532	545	561	581	602	625	650
Dâmbovita-Model_36	Forecast	1226	1313	1399	1486	1572	1659	1745	1832	1918	2005	2091
	UCL	1551	1639	1727	1815	1903	1991	2079	2167	2255	2343	2431
	LCL	902	987	1071	1156	1241	1326	1411	1496	1581	1666	1751
Giurgiu-Model_37	Forecast	430	460	489	518	548	577	607	636	665	695	724
	UCL	623	732	822	903	978	1049	1116	1180	1243	1303	1362
	LCL	238	188	156	134	117	106	97	92	88	86	86
Ialomita-Model_38	Forecast	477	508	540	571	603	634	666	697	729	760	792
	UCL	588	666	733	794	852	907	961	1013	1063	1113	1162
	LCL	365	350	347	348	353	361	371	382	394	408	422
Prahova-Model_39	Forecast	2385	2547	2708	2869	3030	3192	3353	3514	3675	3837	3998
	UCL	3007	3426	3785	4113	4421	4715	4998	5273	5541	5803	6061
	LCL	1763	1667	1631	1625	1640	1668	1707	1755	1810	1870	1935
Teleorman-Model_40	Forecast	563	601	640	679	718	756	795	834	873	911	950
	UCL	655	733	801	864	925	984	1041	1096	1151	1205	1258
	LCL	470	470	479	493	510	529	550	571	594	618	642
Bucuresti - Ilfov-Model_41	Forecast	11240	11841	12442	13043	13644	14245	14846	15447	16048	16649	17249
	UCL	12280	12898	13516	14133	14750	15367	15983	16600	17216	17832	18448
	LCL	10200	10784	11369	11953	12538	13123	13708	14294	14879	15465	16051
Bucuresti-Model_42	Forecast	9373	9826	10280	10733	11187	11640	12094	12547	13001	13454	13907
	UCL	10330	10800	11270	11740	12209	12678	13147	13616	14085	14553	15021
	LCL	8415	8852	9289	9726	10164	10602	11040	11478	11916	12355	12794

Ilfov-Model_43	Forecast	1885	2025	2164	2304	2443	2582	2722	2861	3001	3140	3279
	UCL	2033	2296	2580	2882	3201	3535	3883	4245	4619	5005	5403
	LCL	1738	1754	1749	1725	1685	1630	1560	1477	1382	1275	1156
Macroregiunea patru-Model_44	Forecast	12016	12678	13341	14004	14666	15329	15991	16654	17316	17979	18641
	UCL	14020	14692	15364	16037	16709	17381	18054	18726	19398	20070	20742
	LCL	10012	10665	11318	11970	12623	13276	13929	14582	15234	15887	16540
Sud-Vest Oltenia-Model_45	Forecast	4992	5335	5679	6023	6367	6711	7055	7399	7742	8086	8430
	UCL	5776	6124	6471	6819	7167	7515	7862	8210	8558	8905	9253
	LCL	4207	4547	4887	5227	5567	5907	6247	6587	6927	7268	7608
Dolj-Model_46	Forecast	1646	1752	1858	1963	2069	2175	2281	2387	2492	2598	2704
	UCL	1957	2065	2172	2280	2387	2494	2601	2709	2816	2923	3031
	LCL	1335	1439	1543	1647	1751	1856	1960	2064	2169	2273	2377
Gorj-Model_47	Forecast	997	1065	1132	1199	1266	1334	1401	1468	1535	1603	1670
	UCL	1108	1221	1323	1420	1514	1605	1694	1781	1867	1953	2037
	LCL	887	908	940	978	1019	1063	1108	1155	1204	1253	1303
Mehedinti-Model_48	Forecast	642	686	731	776	821	865	910	955	1000	1044	1089
	UCL	820	938	1040	1132	1219	1302	1382	1459	1534	1608	1680
	LCL	464	434	423	419	422	429	439	451	465	481	498
Olt-Model_49	Forecast	682	729	776	823	871	918	965	1012	1059	1106	1153
	UCL	813	861	908	956	1004	1051	1099	1147	1195	1242	1290
	LCL	552	598	645	691	737	784	830	877	923	970	1016
Vâlcea-Model_50	Forecast	1053	1127	1201	1274	1348	1422	1495	1569	1642	1716	1790
	UCL	1213	1287	1362	1436	1510	1585	1659	1734	1808	1882	1957
	LCL	894	967	1040	1113	1185	1258	1331	1404	1477	1550	1623
Vest-Model_51	Forecast	7696	8213	8729	9246	9763	10279	10796	11312	11829	12346	12862
	UCL	9463	9988	10514	11039	11564	12090	12615	13140	13665	14190	14716
	LCL	5929	6437	6945	7453	7961	8469	8977	9485	9993	10501	11009

Arad-Model_52	Forecast	2347	2514	2682	2849	3017	3184	3352	3519	3687	3854	4022
	UCL	3033	3485	3870	4222	4551	4865	5167	5460	5746	6024	6298
	LCL	1660	1544	1493	1477	1482	1503	1536	1578	1628	1684	1746
Caras-Severin-Model_53	Forecast	866	929	992	1055	1118	1181	1244	1308	1371	1434	1497
	UCL	969	1033	1097	1161	1226	1290	1354	1418	1482	1546	1610
	LCL	762	824	886	949	1011	1073	1135	1198	1260	1322	1384
Hunedoara-Model_54	Forecast	1366	1449	1531	1614	1697	1779	1862	1945	2027	2110	2193
	UCL	1967	2052	2138	2223	2309	2395	2480	2566	2651	2737	2822
	LCL	765	845	925	1005	1084	1164	1244	1324	1403	1483	1563
Timis-Model_55	Forecast	3008	3203	3399	3594	3789	3984	4179	4374	4569	4764	4959
	UCL	3569	3767	3964	4162	4360	4558	4756	4953	5151	5349	5546
	LCL	2448	2640	2833	3025	3217	3410	3602	3794	3987	4179	4372

9. Conclusion:

In conclusion, this paper provides a comprehensive examination of developments in the Arts, Entertainment, Recreation sectors, and other service activities in the Romanian Mountain Area from 2008 to 2018. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the region's cultural vibrancy, offering valuable insights for policymakers, cultural institutions, and researchers. The paper concludes with reflections on potential trajectories and recommendations for sustaining the growth of these vital sectors.

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